

The Importance of Working Hours for Employee Productivity

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Abstract: This article examines the existence of several factors that affect the effectiveness of employees. The most important of them was working hours. Here are some solid facts from various reliable sites about how working hours can have a huge impact on an employee's productivity. In addition, the hypothesis that the employees who choose their own working hours will achieve more results compared to the working hours chosen by the company was found to be true. Qualitative and quantitative data were used to prove the validity of the hypothesis, and a survey of 17 participants was conducted. All the data presented showed the importance of working hours on employee productivity.

Key words: Health, Stress, Productivity, Effects of Shorter Hours, Job Satisfaction.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This article examines the factors needed to improve employee productivity. First of all, there are several factors that affect the productivity of employees, and the main factor of them is working hours, which was determined based on the survey. This article highlights how short or long working hours can affect companies and employees. In addition, it has been proven on the basis of clear facts that it is possible to achieve better results by reducing some unnecessary tasks.

About working hours and productivity

Productivity

A person's level of productivity is determined by how well they finish a task. Partial factor and multifaceted, or total productivity, are the two main types of productivity. Labor, capital, equipment, materials, and so forth are examples of partial factor inputs. The ratio for total input to total output is known as multifactor efficiency. It represents the total effect of all the resources needed to produce the output units. Greater output from the same amount of input is referred to as increased productivity. It indicates a business or industry can convert resources into commodities more efficiently. Productivity increase, therefore, is our chance to produce more with less. Economic development is fueled by improved efficiency, which allows an economy to create and utilize more and more products and offerings for a comparable quantity of labor. A rise in productivity may benefit all facets of society, including businesses, workers, and consumers. It is essential for analysts, companies, and people. The effectiveness with which activities along with goals are accomplished within an organization is determined by employee efficiency. It is the proportion between the input and output of a team or a particular person. Nonetheless, managers

must comprehend the distinction between input and outcome since a variety of internal and external factors can impact an organization's productivity. The labor productivity equation may be employed for determining staff productivity: Total input divided by total output (Simplilearn, 2022).

Working hours

An employee's working hours are the times they are required to carry out their employment responsibilities. The company's internal labour laws, shift schedules, and, in the event that they are not available, the employment contract, will determine working hours. In Uzbekistan, an employee's typical workweek cannot consist of more than forty hours. In a six-day workweek, the daily workday cannot last longer than seven hours, and in a five-day workweek, it cannot exceed eight hours. Employees with impairments in groups I and II should not work more than six hours a day in a six-day workweek, or seven hours and thirty minutes in a five-day workweek. Employees may seek part-time employment when they are hired or at any time thereafter. Pay for part-time workers is determined by how much work they do or how much time they spend working. Annual leave, work experience, and other labour rights are unaffected by part-time employment. Pregnant women, parents of children under 14, and anybody looking after a sick family member must have their requests for part-time employment approved by their employers, as verified by a medical document. Workers must have a minimum of 30 minutes and a maximum of 2 hours to relax and eat during the workday. Working time does not include this break. There must be at least 12 hours of rest each day between the end of the workday and the beginning of the next day's work. Work completed in two or more shifts is referred to as shift work. It is used when the production process takes longer than the allotted amount of time for a workday. The employer will decide on shift work arrangements. Workers must evenly switch shifts. Employing a worker for two consecutive shifts is forbidden. Between shifts, workers must take at least 12 hours of rest each day.

Each person has different levels of energy, cycles of production, and preferred hours of work and approaches. For some folks, 8 hours a day could be the best work plan. Others, however, may encounter increased stress and a decline in productivity. The foundation of any the company's differentiation is productivity. But tracking the hours a staff member works is only one aspect of determining production. Staff efficiency and hours worked must be properly balanced between employers and employees. Additionally, managers need to comprehend the concept of staff efficiency, pinpoint the factors that influence it, and look into the relationship between efficiency and hours spent.

Work time and productivity are not the same thing. Productivity is the amount of important, high-quality work that gets finished in a specific amount of time. An employee's hours worked indicate how long they have been employed.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Leonard-Călin Abrudan, Marian Adrian Burcea, and Mirabela-Constante Matei (2024) examined the impact of working hours on productivity across several sectors and occupational situations. The study's conclusion that productivity and hours worked had a significant inverse relationship was one of its main findings. The study found that, contrary to popular belief, productivity declined as hours worked rose. By examining elements including burnout, exhaustion, diminished motivation, and compromised cognitive function linked to extended work hours, the study investigated the ramifications of this negative trend. The results underscore the significance of reconsidering conventional ideas about working hours and output. Organizations can gain by assignment prioritization, goal-setting, and the application of efficient time management techniques rather than concentrating just on the quantity of hours done. Acknowledging the advantages of working more efficiently over a longer period of time may result in improved output, worker satisfaction, and organizational success. In addition to offering insightful information for people, organizations, and policymakers looking to enhance performance in the modern workplace, this study adds to the continuing discussion on work optimization techniques.

Collewet and Sauermann, (2020) states that when variations in the number of hours worked by the same person across days and weeks due to central planning are taken into account, the impact of working hours

on productivity may be assessed. It was discovered that as agents work more hours, their average handling time per call rises, indicating a decrease in productivity. This finding implies that, even in positions involving part-time employees, weariness may be a significant factor.

2.1 The impact of working hours on employee performance

Long hours: Working longer hours may first seem like a good idea, but research shows that there are a lot of cons as well. People who work over 49 hours a week are less productive, per a Stanford University research. They found that workers who put in 70 hours do the same amount of work as those who put in 55, while this decline increases until it would be pointless to put in any more.

Short hours: The increase in employee efficiency is mostly due to tech. The majority of employees probably don't need to work as many hours as previous generations did. Many companies are experimenting with the four-day workweek with positive outcomes, despite the fact that workers aren't working 40 hours during those four days. Companies who adopted the four-day strategy saw lower employee turnover and absence rates. Employees that work 32 hours a week as opposed to 40 have said they are happy. These workers are able to manage their stress, sleep better, and workout more. They also have more time to spend with their loved ones.

Flexible Hours: Offering workers flexible hours, which allow them to choose where and when they want to complete their responsibilities, is becoming more and more popular in the culture of the workplace. Forty-three percent of employees who had flexible work schedules reported being happier and more efficient, according to Gartner. This is partly explained by the fact that thirty percent of employees say that working less time has made them more productive (Sarwar, 2024).

3.0 HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis: *Employees who choose their own hours are more productive than those who have a fixed schedule.*

The advantages of working flexible hours include better results, a healthier balance between work and life, and less anxiety at work. Its drawbacks include unclear boundaries, poor communication, and a lack of organization (Brouge, 2024). Businesses may achieve higher overall performance and employee retention by allowing employees to choose their own hours, whether it be through a maxiflex schedule, compacted schedule, or any alternate work arrangement. A minor adjustment can have a significant impact. According to a study by the time-tracking software DeskTime, 59.1% of companies that hire office workers now provide flexible work schedules (Johnson, 2022).

Establishing work hours has several advantages, such as enhanced teamwork, distinct work-life boundaries, and consistent habits. Fixed working hours have the drawbacks of a strict schedule, more stress, and less personal flexibility (Brouge, 2024). Currently, 40.9% of companies offer fixed hours, according DeskTime statistics. A strategy like this might also benefit the welfare of the employees (Johnson, 2022).

3.1 Survey

In order to prove the hypothesis, a survey was conducted among 17 people from 18 to 26 years old working in various fields. Survey questions was:

How old are you?

Do you work?

How working hours play a role in your performance?

Do you get more results if you choose your working hours yourself or if the company chooses them for you?

The results were as follows.

1 How old are you? 17 респондента

3 How working hours play a role in your performance ? 17 респондента

4 Do you get more results if you choose your working hours yourself, or if the company chooses them for you? 17 респондента

I get more results by choosing my own working hours	100.0%	17 votes
I get more results with the time the company chooses	0.0%	0 votes
There is no difference at all	0.0%	0 votes

Based on the results of the survey, it can be said that 12 out of 17 participants have a high concern for good results, 2 have an average and 3 have no difference at all. But all 17 participants said that they would achieve more results if they chose their working hours.

The results of quantitative and qualitative data show that our hypothesis is correct, that is, employees who choose their own hours are more productive than those who have a fixed schedule.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

This paper's goal was to investigate how working hours affect employee productivity. To this end, primary and secondary techniques were employed. All required data is gathered from trustworthy sources. The literature review's data came from statistics data and internet publications. Scholarly sources were also looked up on Google Scholar, yielding data from 2020 to 2024. Finding out what employees in different professions thought was the aim of the poll that was done for the article. 17 participants received the survey from suncake.com. The poll was completed by staff members from a variety of disciplines, and qualitative information on the hypothesis's viability was gathered from additional sources.

5.0 ANALYSIS

First, this analysis's findings from surveys in a variety of sectors indicated that everyone's performance is higher when they choose their own working hours. Furthermore, the outcomes of employees who put in 70 hours and those who put in 55 hours are same, based on the statistics above. Workers who put in 70 hours a week might also get better outcomes by cutting back on their working hours using these suggestions. Give workers the right equipment. With the correct resources, staff members may complete tasks quickly and effectively while meeting deadlines. Put an end to pointless gatherings. Long meetings that aren't essential are frequently dull and don't get the desired outcomes. Employees are less engaged in these meetings as well since they are less productive and efficient. A Salary.com poll indicates that fifty percent of employees believe meetings are the top time waster at work. Consequently, eliminating pointless meetings is another practical way to boost productivity and worker happiness. The distractions should be turned off. Interruptions are one of the main things that prevent teammates from working efficiently, regardless of whether they are on-site or remote. Workers spend an average of 2.5 hours a day coping with disturbances, according to study. Additionally, it takes them an average of 23 minutes and 15 seconds to refocus. As a result, it is critical that businesses give their employees a serene workplace. Consequently, the productivity and working conditions are at their best. Keep an eye on worker productivity. There are several ways for businesses to gauge yield. Among these strategies is the identification of productivity gaps. These gaps are brought on by working more hours, having too much

work, not receiving enough training, or using the incorrect equipment. By keeping a close eye on employee behavior, managers may spot situations that create the most productive workplace and provide tactics to increase output. Working remotely. Employees seek autonomy and flexibility in their working environments after the epidemic. It's critical to be mindful and realize that employees won't misuse their increased authority. Instead, they would rather work when they are feeling very productive. Due to this flexibility, remote team members put in over 40 hours a week, which is 43 percent more than their counterparts in traditional offices. As a result, working remotely can yield outcomes that are on par with or even better than working on-site.

6.0 DISCUSSION

Decision Making. The main purpose of this paper's analysis was to examine the importance of working hours in the productivity of workers. During the analysis, a survey was conducted among 17 participants working in various fields to prove the hypothesis by considering the necessary information and facts from various magazines and sites. The main purpose of the survey was to prove the hypothesis and find out the opinion of employees working in various fields. Almost all the participants mentioned that working hours play a big role in achieving results. In addition, according to a study conducted by Stanford University, employees who work 70 hours and employees who work 55 hours show the same result. Therefore, even if the company reduced the hours of its employees, it would benefit both the employee and the company. For example, employee turnover will be reduced, work-life balance and so on. There are several types of reduction of working hours of company employees. For example, providing employees with the necessary tools on time. It is possible to reduce the organization of various meetings during working hours, or to organize a meeting only on a certain day, for example, every Monday. Limiting the use of unnecessary things by employees during working hours, for example, phones. It should only be allowed to be used for a certain period of time or when it is very important. Another way is to track employee productivity. By using these types, the company will have active workers without any losses by reducing the working hours of the workers.

7.0 CONCLUSION

In this study, it can be concluded that the productivity of employees is affected by working hours. The company should know the opinion of employees, take it into account, support employees and work together. If the wants and desires of employees are not taken into account, no matter how much they use them, they will have the same result. And as a result of this, employee turnover increases and the potential for work productivity decreases.

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